

Design of the Slope Detection Circuit for On-Chip Current Sensing

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Abstract—This paper presents a design and analysis of the slope detection circuit for on-chip sensing of load current in DC-DC converters. The proposed indirect sensing approach is based on measurement of the output voltage slope across the filtering capacitor during the discharging phase. Thus, information about the slope of output voltage can be further used for rather effective control of switches in the converter. The slope detector circuit was designed in standard 65 nm CMOS technology using the nominal supply voltage of 1.2 V and can be used for current sensing within the range from one to hundreds of mA. Since the proposed circuit has mainly digital character, the robustness to process, temperature and supply voltage variations can be ensured rather conveniently.

Keywords—current sensing methods, voltage drop, slope detector, low-power and low-voltage design, CMOS technology.

I. INTRODUCTION

Recent development and research of portable electronic devices are mainly focused on the low-power and low-voltage design as well as integration of the complex mixed-signal system on a single chip. Usually, the most power-hungry sub-circuit of such complex Systems-on-chip (SoC) is the analog part. Therefore, in most cases, information about the particular load or current consumption can bring an effective approach to decrease energy demand of the whole SoC. Moreover, development in IC fabrication leads to advanced technologies that exhibit remarkable variations of process parameters, and thus the process-voltage-temperature (PVT) robustness is one of the most challenging tasks for integrated circuit designers and researchers. This issue becomes even more important if speaking about high-precision circuits.

The known value of electrical current flowing through a certain circuit might be very helpful for controlling the other parts of a system. The controller of DC-DC converters is a good example of a system, where the electric current can be used as a control signal. The flyback DC-DC converter is classified as a simple topology of isolated converter that is widely used as the power supply circuit in cellphones, notebooks, personal computers, LCD TVs, and other portable devices [1]. The schematic diagram of a flyback DC-DC converter is depicted in Fig. 1.

A transformer is used in the flyback converter for energy storage, input-output isolation and output power transformation [2]. Operation of the flyback converter is rather simple. If a MOS transistor switch is turned-on, energy from the input DC source is stored in the primary winding of the transformer. When the switch is turned-off, stored energy is transferred to the secondary winding. Energy conversion efficiency of the converter might be improved by sensing the load current and switching the power MOS switch in a proper way. It is rather obvious that the current sensing has to be performed on-chip.

Fig. 1. General diagram of a flyback DC-DC converter

On-chip current sensing techniques are usually based on direct approach to current measurement, where a sensing element is used. Here, a shunt resistor, a MOS transistor connected as resistor or sensing transistor connected in parallel with the power MOS device are used to sense the electric current [3], [4], [5], [6], [7], [8]. The main properties and features of such techniques are described in more detail in [5]. However, the main disadvantages of direct approaches include low accuracy and rather high power losses across the sensing element. On the other hand, indirect approaches offer possibility to sense current without a need for additional sensing element connected in series, and therefore, represent the lossless techniques for on-chip current measurement. These techniques use other electrical parameter that is directly related to the sensed current. Thus, indirect methods do not influence the parameters of a measured circuit through additional hardware.

In this paper, we present the slope detector circuit designed in 65nm CMOS technology, which can be used for indirect on-chip current measurement and then, controlling the flyback

DC-DC converter. In Section II, the basic idea behind the designed slope detector is described. The achieved results obtained by simulations are presented in Section III, and some conclusions are drawn in Section IV.

II. PROPOSED SLOPE DETECTOR

The proposed slope detector (SD) circuit is based on a principle depicted in Fig. 2. Since the designed slope detector intended to be used in the controller of DC-DC converter, the load current can be indirectly sensed through the converter output voltage. This approach is based on an assumption of using a large bypass capacitor at the output of DC-DC converter. In such a case, during the discharging phase of capacitor C_L , the output voltage will vary linearly in time. The sensed current I_{sens} depends on the output voltage V_{sens} , the load resistor R_L as well as the output capacitor C_L , and can be expressed as follows:

$$I_{sens} = \frac{V_{sens}}{R_L} \cdot e^{-\frac{t}{R_L C_L}} \approx \frac{V_{sens}}{R_L}, \quad (1)$$

where we considered that $t/R_L C_L \rightarrow 0$. This assumption can be ensured if either the measurement is carried out in a short time interval or the capacitor discharging time constant $t/R_L C_L$ will be large. Thus, if one of these two conditions is ensured, the electric current can be conveniently sensed in the indirect manner by measuring the slope of voltage across the capacitor C_L within its discharging phase.

Fig. 2. Output voltage slope detection principle

The slope of output voltage is measured within a selected time window which is given by two voltage reference levels V_{R_FH} and V_{R_FL} (denoted as the voltage window V in Fig. 2). In such a case, the respective electric current will be given as:

$$I_{sens} = C_L \cdot \frac{V}{T} = \frac{V_{R_FL}}{t_L} \frac{V_{R_FH}}{t_H}, \quad (2)$$

It is important to note that accuracy of the proposed current measurement approach can be influenced by process, temperature and supply voltage variations. Such fluctuations are not considered in equation (3) but these will be further investigated in the following part of the paper.

The circuit block diagram of the designed slope detector is depicted in Fig. 3. The converter output voltage V_{sens} across the capacitor C_L is sensed by two comparators (K1 and K2) forming so-called a window comparator. Both comparators are

based on a common used topology with hysteresis introduced to protect the circuit from unwanted glitches at the comparator output. Digital outputs of K1 and K2 comparators are used to start/stop the counter which is driven by external CLK signal with frequency of 1 MHz. In order to extend the range of possible slope that can be detected, the input frequency is decreased and multiplexed to the input of counter. This simple feature brings possibility of sensing a wider range of currents. After the counter stops counting, its value can be easily compared to the reference value stored in a Look-Up-Table (LUT), and the measured current is evaluated.

Fig. 3. Block diagram of proposed slope detector

Since the window comparator circuit was employed to sense the voltage at capacitor C_L , it can be rather sensitive to process variations, especially the input offset voltage, and consequently, delay of both comparators might influence the overall accuracy of the proposed measurement method. For this reason, equation (3) needs to be extended as follows:

$$I_{sens} = C_L \cdot \frac{V}{T} = \frac{V_{R_FL}}{t_L} \frac{V_{R_FH} \pm V_{off}}{t_H \pm t_d}, \quad (3)$$

where V_{off} and t_d is difference of the input offset voltage and the transition delay of comparators (K1 and K2), respectively. Difference in these parameters will be mainly influenced by mismatch of devices forming the comparators. On the other hand, the proposed slope detector will be more robust to the variations of CMOS process itself. In the following paragraph, the proposed SD circuit is analyzed in detail.

In Fig. 4, the following waveforms are depicted (from top to bottom): comparator reference voltage inputs (VREF_H and VREF_L), outputs of the window comparator circuit (COMP_H and COMP_L), and finally, clock signal (CLK) and the counter output (Count). The counter output is set to zero by the external global reset and then, its value is incremented by each rising edge of the clock signal CLK. The comparator outputs (K1 - green color and K2 - red color) without hysteresis and transition delay are depicted using solid line in the middle graph. Since the functionality

of the window comparator circuits is fully asynchronous and its outputs do not depend on the clock signal, a measurement error occurs labeled as t_{clk} . In this case, the maximum value of error delay between the first rise edge of clock signal in measuring time window and the falling edge of comparator K1 output (COMP_H) can be less than one period of the clock signal. The same measurement error may occur at the end of measuring time window because the rising edge of comparator K2 output (COMP_L) is not synchronized with the rising edge of clock signal either. V_1 and V_2 represent the hysteresis of comparators K1 and K2, which has the same value for both comparators. Due to presence of hysteresis, the output signal of comparators K1 and K2 will be delayed (t_1 and t_2). Delayed comparator outputs and the counter value are depicted by dashed lines. Differences between t_1 of comparator K1 and t_2 of comparator K2 are kept within nanosecond range (across the process corners), which is still acceptable since no significant influence to the measuring time window is observed.

III. CHIEVED RESULTS

The results obtained by simulation of the proposed slope detector circuit are presented in this section. In simulations, fabrication process fluctuations were taken into account, and the designed circuit was analyzed using Corner and Monte Carlo (MC) analyses. The temperature range from -20 C to $+85$ C was considered in all simulations.

Dependence of the counter finite value on the sensed voltage slope is depicted in Fig. 5. These results were obtained from Corner and MC analyses. Since the proposed slope detector is based on counting the clock pulses in a selected time window,

Fig. 4. Operation of the SD circuit

this concept is robust against the fabrication process variations. Indeed, the concept is sensitive only to the mismatch between devices forming the comparators K1 and K2.

Fig. 5. Dependence of the counter finite value on the sensed voltage slope

From Fig. 5 and Fig. 6, it can be observed that the device mismatch can cause variation of the finite counter value by a standard deviation of ± 6 pulses counted by the counter. If we consider variations of $\pm 3\sigma$, the finite value of counted pulses can vary in the range from 138 to 172, while the mean value will be 159. This result represents the total error of the proposed approach, and was achieved while taking into account mismatch of all devices used in the proposed SD circuit.

Fig. 6. Monte Carlo analysis: for slope=150 V/s

The second part of the measurement error is caused by t_{clk} depicted in Fig. 4 and explained in the previous section. In Fig. 7, t_{clk} error over the process corners for slope of 150 V/s is shown. As one can observe, the t_{clk} can vary over the process corners and can cause the measurement error of almost 2 μ s. This means (for the input frequency of 1 MHz) that in a process corner, t_{clk} can have an undesired effect on the finite counter value by 1 to 2 additional pulses counted by the counter. It is important to note that t_{clk} was analyzed for different values of slope, and in the most cases, the measurement error of maximum 2 μ s was observed. In Fig. 8, result of Monte Carlo analysis for t_{clk} error at slope of 150 V/s is depicted. If we consider variations of $\pm 3\sigma$, the value of t_{clk} can vary in the range from 1.512 μ s to 2.506 μ s, while the mean value will be 1.955 μ s.

In order to analyze robustness of the proposed slope detector further, variations of the time window were achieved for all

Fig. 7. l_k error for slope=150 V/s

Fig. 8. Monte Carlo analysis: l_k error for slope=150 V/s

process corners and the whole temperature range. The time window variation for different values of slope is illustrated in Fig. 9. It can be observed that the absolute value of time window is not kept the same for different values of slope but it does not vary over the process corners. Unfortunately, the device mismatch (within K1 and K2) can cause additional measurement error, and therefore, sophisticated layout techniques have to be employed. Monte Carlo analysis of time window variation for slope=150 V/s is shown in Fig. 10. The value of time window can vary in the range from 369.1 μ s to 424.7 μ s, while the mean value will be 398.041 μ s. In this analysis, variation of $\pm 3\sigma$ was considered.

Fig. 9. Variations of time window over the process corners

In Fig. 11, layout of the developed SD circuit is shown. Dimensions of implemented layout is 62 μ m x 265 μ m and thus, the SD occupies chip area of 0.016 mm^2 . Most of the

total area is taken by comparators. However, implemented comparators have also additional functions (hysteresis tune and calibration features) needed for testing of the chip prototype.

Fig. 10. Monte Carlo analysis: Variations of time window

Fig. 11. Layout of the proposed slope detector

IV. CONCLUSION

novel indirect approach for on-chip current sensing based on the output voltage slope measurement is presented. The proposed concept of slope detector shows good robustness against the process and temperature variations. Nevertheless, very good matching of devices needs to be ensured to reduce mismatch and improve the overall accuracy of current measurement. Thus, further improvement can be reached by employing calibration/trimming of the comparator input voltage as well as through using a synchronous comparator. The proposed approach and the developed SD circuit can be used in a DC-DC converter system to measure the load current or to estimate the output current for the purpose of effective control of the whole converter. Our research activities in near future will be mainly focused on evaluation of the prototype chip samples.

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